

Abstract

EVALUATION OF MICROBIAL COUNTS IN APPLE FLAVORED BEER COMPARED TO BASE BEER AFTER EXPOSING TO EXTERNAL ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

Fermented apple beverages are popular worldwide, with specifications in each country. This product is commonly known as apple cider. Apple cider is an alcoholic beverage produced from the fermented juice of apples. Lion Brewery (Ceylon) PLC. has theorized on brewing recipes and techniques to produce an apple flavored beer, which is similar to apple cider in taste. Considering the microbial stability of fermented beverages; due to its low pH, high alcohol and presence of hop compounds, base beer has remarkable microbial stability when they are exposed to the external environment. The addition of fructose, glucose, apple flavor and absence of hop compounds makes flavored beer more vulnerable to microbial growth than the base beer. Many studies have been carried out to investigate how storage condition affects beer deterioration and shelf-life. Besides, studies carried out in the context of flavored beer is very limited. In the beer industry, the proper crowning of beer bottles is a critical point when comes to food safety. there is an unavoidable percentage of improperly crowned product found on the market because of machine errors. The objective of this study is to evaluate microbial counts after lifting the crown from apple flavored beer compared to the same alcohol strength base beer. Moreover, identification of beer spoilage organisms, non-beer-spoilage organisms, rapidly growing or slowly growing microbes, etc. done during the study period. Thus, to meet this objective microbial assessment, including total cell counts, viable cell counts, and microbial identification tests were carried out on a daily basis for samples exposed to external surroundings for six continues days. Each experiment was repeated five times using the universal beer agar medium. The results clearly illustrated that there was a clear positive impact on microbial growth due to the presence of apple flavor and the absence of hops built a suitable environment for non-hop resistance microbes. Beer spoilage microbes such as wild yeasts, *Brenttanomyces sp.*, *Lactobacillus sp.*, *Pedicoccus sp.* and non-beer spoilage microbes like *Pichia sp.*, *Candida sp.*, *Henssanula sp.* were clearly distinguished. Moreover, further studies are needed to confirm these preliminary findings.

Keywords: Flavored beer, Deterioration, Food safety, Microbial diversity, Hop resistance